

Does prince necessarily cite sleeping beauty?

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Introduction

Some high-impact papers experience undervaluation from the science community, known as “sleeping beauty” (van Raan, 2004); thereby, any solutions to identify under-estimated research are needed. The discovery of sleeping beauty can be viewed as a long-span knowledge diffusion process by papers called prince; hence prince identification is a direct approach to solve the problem. Conceptually, prince has played the role of (1) giving information value, (2) creating access channels, and (3) developing user demand for sleeping beauty (Wang, 2012), but scientometrics has provided practical tools to find potential sleeping beauty finders (Song et al., 2018). Generally, prince identification is explored by direct citing papers to sleeping beauty before its awakening (van Raan, 2004), assuming that the prince’s authors consciously recognize the importance of hidden discovery and cite the paper before the awakening. However, it may not always be the case. For instance, Chang’s novel smart card authentication scheme (Chang & Hwang, 1993) was most co-cited with Hwang’s advanced scheme (Hwang & Li, 2000), but it did not cite sleeping beauty. It could be because Hwang’s work contributed to the researcher’s attention toward the smart card’s capability and indirectly influenced Chang’s citations. Such indirect impact is also reported in COVID-19 sleeping beauties that recent papers indirectly affect beyond the direct citation (Turki et al., 2022).

In this paper, we examined the indirect effect of prince papers. Prince is inductively defined as the most co-cited paper with sleeping beauty in its awakening period; in other words, spreading the findings into the academic community. There are two research questions to be solved.

1. How many princes directly cite sleeping beauty?
2. What disciplines prefer an indirect prince effect?

Materials and Methods

Sleeping beauty is defined as an article or conference proceeding that received less than one citation per year for the first ten years but then had at least five citations per year in the next five years in Scopus. From the 30 million papers published during 1970–2006, with plenty of time to observe sleep and burst transition, 4,275 papers were determined as sleeping beauties. For disciplinary analysis, we obtained the

research field of each paper from the clustering of the citation network (Wang & Eck, 2012).

The prince is inductively defined as the most co-cited paper with sleeping beauty during its awakening period $t_{SB}+10 \sim t_{SB}+14$, in which t_{SB} represents the publication year of each sleeping beauty. Co-citation from papers during the awakening period demonstrates that the researchers at the time considered the knowledge connection between the pair, so the paper contributed to the expansion of focal sleeping papers. We validated whether these prince papers explicitly noticed the knowledge connection at that time.

Results

Fig.1 shows the preliminary results of the co-citation rate of max co-cited papers during the awakening. Compared with null publications which obtained the same number of citations in the first five years as sleeping beauties obtained during $t_{SB}+10 \sim t_{SB}+14$, sleeping beauties are more co-cited with a specific paper. In short, the co-citation connection was stronger for sleeping beauty than null papers, providing the significance of the prince’s information awakening compared with the ordinary knowledge diffusion process.

Figure 1. Co-citation rate with the max co-cited paper during the awakening. The dotted line represents the average of the rate.

Our finding is that most co-cited papers during the awakening period would rather not cite sleeping beauty (Tab.1, $2895/4275=67.7\%$). It shows that sleeping beauty is usually awakened by the cultivation of indirect princes beyond simple explanation through direct citation. Moreover, some prince was published even after their awakening ($521/4275=12.2\%$). The result objectively reveals that the ideal prince case (citing sleeping beauty

before the awakening) is just part of the cases (1077/4275=25.2%).

Table 1. Prince relation and publication year for 4,275 sleeping beauties.

	Prince publication year		
	$t_{SB} \sim t_{SB}+9$ (before)	$t_{SB}+10 \sim t_{SB}+14$ (after)	Total
Cite SB (direct)	1,077	303	1,380
Not cite SB (indirect)	2,677	218	2,895
Total	3,754	521	4,275

Considering the discipline, all research fields prefer indirect princes for intra-field connections, but inter-field connections are more likely to be indirect contributions, showing that interdisciplinary princes unconsciously boost sleeping beauties (Fig.2).

Figure 2. A relative number of indirect citations by princes. >0.5 means the indirect contribution preference. -1 refers to the absence of samples.

Discussions

Indirect dominance of the prince's contribution toward sleeping beauty emphasizes the value of unconscious knowledge connection beyond direct citation. Smart card work described in the Introduction is the typical case. Albeit Hwang's prince did not directly cite Chang's sleeping beauty, nurturing technological advancement of smart cards makes researchers pay more attention to the topic. If it is true, a group of sleeping beauties or princes may collect the bulk of findings in an organized fashion. A network science approach would solve the problem and visualize the group's awakening. Some research has already pointed out the 'cluster' of princes (Teixeira et al., 2020), but more detailed analyses are still needed.

Besides, a stronger co-citation rate of sleeping beauty than ordinary papers implies that the long-span knowledge diffusion requires a 'splint.' Short-span knowledge diffusion does not depend on a specific paper to spread the novelty of findings, rather becomes the base of various topics like tree-

structured knowledge propagation. That may be why the highest co-citation rate of ordinary papers is low. On the other hand, long-span knowledge diffusion prefers a strong bond with a particular paper for propagating the knowledge; hence it might usually be in a specific context to discuss the novelty of sleeping beauty. Subsequently, identifying a context-making prince has been the key to discovering hidden beauties.

Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced direct and indirect princes toward sleeping beauty's awakening to answer how many princes defined by inductive approach through co-citations with sleeping beauty during the awakening period directly cite sleeping beauty. Subsequently, most prince indirectly contributes to the information awakening more strongly than normally cited papers. This result implies the significance of the group-based approach (direct and indirect effect) in explaining the sleeping beauty phenomenon. Toward deeper understanding, a network-based approach including the macro-level structure of knowledge connections and more detailed case studies are needed for future work.

Acknowledgments

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